

Kinetics of Catalysed Esterification of Propionic Acid with various Alcohols using Synthetic Cation Exchange Resin

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Kinetics of esterification of ethyl, 2-propyl and 1-butyl alcohols with propionic acid have been investigated using SBPF (styrene-butadiene-phenolformaldehyde) synthetic cation exchange resin (in H⁺-form). The experimental data are found to fit a second order bimolecular kinetic equation. The influence of molecular weight, structure of alcohols, amount of catalyst (H⁺-ion), molar ratio of reactants and reaction temperature on the specific rate constant and percent conversion have been investigated.

The esterification reaction rate constant (K_1) and the percent conversion (X_{Ac} , %) for different alcohols with propionic acid have been calculated and compared. It is found to decrease with increasing molecular weight and branching of alcohols: 2-propanol < 1-butanol < ethanol.

Kinetics of esterification of organic acids in the presence of cation exchanger have been investigated by several authors¹⁻⁵. The esterification reaction concerning the effect of molecular weight and structure of organic acids on the rate of esterification has been experimentally verified^{1,6}. But very few studies have been reported on the influence of molecular weight and structure of alcohols on the rate of esterification reaction^{1,2}. The recent investigations^{7,8} show that the rate of reaction decreases with increasing molecular weight or branching of the acids or alcohols.

The present work reports the kinetics of esterification reactions of ethanol, 2-propanol and 1-butanol with propionic acid using a synthetic cation exchanger (SBPE) in the H⁺-form as a catalyst. The effects of molecular weight, branching, amount of catalyst, molar ratio of reactants and reaction temperature on the rate of esterification reaction and percent conversion have been determined.

Results and Discussion

The specific rate constant (K_1) for the esterification of the propionic acid with ethyl, 2-propyl and 1-butyl alcohols was calculated using the simplified equation⁹.

$$\ln \frac{(X_{eg} - X_A)X_{Ac}}{(X_{Ac} - X_A)X_{eg}} = \frac{2B - (B+1)X_{Ac}}{X_{Ac}} C_{A0} K_1 t \quad (1)$$

$$\text{where, } X_{eg} = \frac{BX_{Ac}}{(B+1)X_{Ac} - B} \quad (2)$$

K_1 is the reaction velocity constant ($\text{dm}^3 \text{g}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$), X_A the fractional conversion of acid, X_{Ac} the fractional conversion of acid at equilibrium, B the molar ratio of reactants (alcohol : acid), C_{A0} the initial concentration of acid and t the time.

By plotting the left-hand-side term of equation (1) against t , the value of K_1 is obtained from the rectilinear relationship. The induction period observed was found to

be 10–15 min. It is evident that the rate constant varies with the different process variables.

Effect of amount of catalyst : The effect of amount of catalyst on the fraction conversion and the rate of acid-catalysed esterification of propionic acid with ethanol, 2-propanol and 1-butanol was investigated and the data are given in Table 1. It could be seen that the values of fractional conversion and the rate constant (K_1) increase with the increase in the amount of catalyst. Our results agree well with those of Thakur and Nageshwar⁶ where they used butanol and methanol with butyric acid in presence of Dowex 50w-XB as a catalyst.

Effect of molar ratio of the reactants^{2,3,5} : The effect of molar ratio of the reactants on the values of fraction conversion and the specific rate constant K_1 for esterification of propionic acid with different studied alcohols was investigated. The results (Table 2) indicate that both the values of the rate of acid-catalysed esterification and the percent conversion (X_{Ac} , %) increase with the increasing amount of molar ratio of the reactants in the order : ethanol > 1-butanol > 2-propanol.

Effect of reaction temperature : The effect of temperature on the rate constant of esterification was investigated by plotting the percent conversion (X_A , %) vs t (plots not shown). The results (Table 3) indicate that the K_1 (the apparent rate constant) of catalysed esterification reaction of propionic acid with the three studied alcohols is markedly influenced with the increase of reaction temperature. It is found that this increasing trend of specific rate constant with the reaction temperature is probably due to the increasing mobility of ions or molecules in the solution¹⁰.

It is clear from the results (Tables 1–3) that the calculated values of ΔG^* would decrease with increasing amount of the resin, molar ratio of reactants and reaction temperature in the following order : ethanol < 2-propanol < 1-butanol. It may be noted that the values of ΔG^* (the change

TABLE 1—REACTION VELOCITY CONSTANTS FOR THE ESTERIFICATION OF PROPIONIC ACID WITH ETHANOL, 2-PROPANOL AND 1-BUTANOL (EFFECT OF AMOUNT OF CATALYST)

W, g	Ethanol at 75°, B = 12					2-Propanol at 80°, B = 12					1-Butanol at 110°, B = 12				
	2	4	6	8	10	2	4	6	8	10	2	4	6	8	10
X _{Ae} , %	86	88	90	93	97	52	66	75	79	84	81	85	88	91	94
K ₁ , 10 ⁻⁵	1.27	2.72	3.68	5.08	6.05	0.40	0.61	0.73	0.85	1.04	0.46	0.69	0.86	0.98	1.28
K ₁ [*] , 10 ⁻⁵	1.09	2.51	3.45	4.82	5.81	0.23	0.41	0.54	0.73	0.87	0.28	0.45	0.50	0.71	0.90
ΔG*, kcal mol ⁻¹	27.24	26.66	26.44	26.20	26.07	28.66	28.24	28.04	27.83	27.71	31.00	30.63	30.56	30.28	28.79

TABLE 2—REACTION VELOCITY CONSTANTS FOR THE ESTERIFICATION OF PROPIONIC ACID WITH ETHANOL, 2-PROPANOL AND 1-BUTANOL (EFFECT OF MOLAR RATIO OF REACTANTS)

B	Ethanol at 75°, W = 10 g				2-Propanol at 80°, W = 10 g				1-Butanol at 110°, W = 10 g			
	3.0	6.0	9.0	12.0	3.0	6.0	9.0	12.0	3.0	6.0	9.0	12.0
X _{Ae} , %	88	92	95	98	73	77	83	88	82	88	91	95
K ₁ , 10 ⁻⁵	3.61	4.70	6.68	8.72	1.01	1.34	1.57	1.74	2.20	3.67	4.63	6.4
K ₁ [*] , 10 ⁻⁵	3.46	4.53	6.53	8.54	0.85	1.16	1.44	1.60	2.04	3.50	4.47	6.2
ΔG*, kcal mol ⁻¹	26.44	26.20	25.99	25.80	27.73	27.50	27.35	27.28	29.48	29.06	28.87	28.6

TABLE 3—REACTION VELOCITY CONSTANTS FOR THE ESTERIFICATION OF PROPIONIC ACID WITH ETHANOL, 2-PROPANOL AND 1-BUTANOL (EFFECT OF REACTION TEMPERATURE)

t, °C	Ethanol at W = 10 g, B = 12				2-Propanol at W = 10 g, B = 12				1-Butanol at W = 10 g, B = 12			
	50	60	70	80	50	60	70	80	50	60	70	80
X _{Ae} , %	88	93	96	97	48	80	90	98	80	85	91	95
K ₁ , 10 ⁻⁵	2.02	4.02	5.13	5.97	0.37	0.51	0.71	1.08	1.16	4.16	5.12	5.49
K ₁ [*] , 10 ⁻⁵	1.85	3.86	4.93	5.81	0.19	0.36	0.52	0.87	0.98	3.94	4.90	5.26
ΔG*, kcal mol ⁻¹	26.07	25.59	25.01	24.73	27.41	27.09	25.92	25.74	27.71	27.12	26.58	26.20
ΔH*, kcal mol ⁻¹	7.92	7.89	7.85	7.80	9.65	9.60	9.54	9.48	10.34	10.25	10.18	10.13
ΔS*, kcal mol ⁻¹	0.101	0.098	0.095	0.092	0.111	0.108	0.105	0.101	0.109	0.105	0.101	0.097
ΔE*, kcal mol ⁻¹	9.214				10.937				11.655			

of free energy of activation) are derived from Eyring's equation,

$$\Delta G^* = -RT \ln K_1^*$$

where, $K_1^* = hK_r/k$; here K_r is the rate constant, k the Boltzmann constant, h the Plank constant. The values of E_a for the catalysed esterification of propionic acid with ethanol, 2-propanol and 1-butanol are found to be in the range of 9–11 kcal mol⁻¹. The thermodynamic function ΔH^* (the change of enthalpy of activation) was evaluated from the relation¹²,

$$\Delta H^* = \frac{d \ln K_r}{dT} = -RT$$

$$\text{or } \Delta H^* = E_a - 2RT$$

Table 3 indicates that the calculated values of ΔH^* decrease with increasing reaction temperature and has the following order : ethanol < 2-propanol < 1-butanol. The values of ΔS^* (the change of entropy of activation) (Table 3) were calculated using the relation,

$$K_r = \frac{kT}{h} e^{\Delta S^*/R} e^{-E/RT}$$

The values exhibited slight decrease with increasing reac-

tion temperature and the results follow the order : 2-propanol > 1-butanol > ethanol.

In general, the conversion percent increases significantly with increase in the amount of catalyst, molar ratio of reactants and reaction temperatures. In all cases the conversion data can be fairly correlated with the molecular reversible kinetic equation reported by Sharma *et al.*³.

Effect of molecular weight : From the data given in Tables 1–3, it can be deduced that the rate of esterification of linear alcohols is high compared to that of the branched ones. It is of interest to compare that the values of the rate constant (K_1) obtained when esterified with 2-propanol are lower than the corresponding values for 1-butanol. Although 1-butanol has a higher molecular weight, its K_1 values was found to be higher than that of 2-propanol. This discrepancy may be due to the presence of branch alkyl group (secondary alcohol) in 2-propanol which leads to hindrance.

The fraction conversion of different alcohols using the same acid (propionic acid) decreases as the molecular weight increases. The values of percent conversion at equilibrium (X_{Ae} , %) (Tables 1–3) are lower in case of 1-butanol than those in case of ethanol. This behaviour could be attributed to the physical constants¹², namely, density,

viscosity, surface tension and dielectric constant, rather than the molecular weight.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either of B.D.H. or E. Merck (G.R.) make.

Styrene-butadiene-phenolformaldehyde (SBPF) cation exchange resin in Na⁺-form was prepared by the reported method¹³. It was converted to H⁺-form by treatment with 10% HCl, washed with distilled water till free from HCl, filtered and dried for 12 h at 50–60°. The selected mesh size of this cation exchange resin was 250–420 μm. The exchange capacity of this synthetic resin was 3.4 meq/g of dry resin.

The esterification reactions were carried out in a three-necked flask placed in a constant temperature bath (±0.1°) fitted with a reflux condenser, a mercury seal stirrer. The flask was charged with propionic acid and portion of selected alcohols. After a brief stirring, the catalyst and the remaining alcohol were added. Samples (2 ml) were taken out at regular intervals for analysis. The unreacted acid³ was determined by titrating against 0.1 M NaOH in presence of an excess of organic alcohols.

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